

UCH O‘LCHOVI DIFFERENSIAL TENGLAMALAR SISTEMASINING MUVOZANAT NUQTALARINING TURLARI

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Annatsiya. Uch o‘lchovli fazoda o‘zgaras koeffsientli bir jinsli differensial tenglamalar sistemasini trayektoriyalarini muvozanat nuqta $O(0,0,0)$ atrofida joylashishini o‘rganiladi.

Kalit so‘zi: Muvozanat, xaraktrestik tenglama, asimtotik, tugun, turg‘unmas, trayektoriya, turg‘un tugun, Turvis sharti, turg‘un fokus, turg‘unmas fokus, focus markaz, karrali haqiqiy va har xil, qo‘shma kompleks turg‘unmas egar, turg‘un tug‘ma tugun.

Bu maqolada o‘zgaras koeffsientli bir jinsli tenglamalar sistemasi uch o‘lchovli fazoda berilgan bo‘lsin

$$\begin{cases} \frac{dx_1}{dt} = a_{11}x_1 + a_{12}x_2 + a_{13}x_3 \\ \frac{dx_2}{dt} = a_{21}x_1 + a_{22}x_2 + a_{23}x_3 \\ \frac{dx_3}{dt} = a_{31}x_1 + a_{32}x_2 + a_{33}x_3 \end{cases} \quad \det A \neq 0, \quad A = (a_{ij}) \quad (1)$$

Sistema traektoriyalarning $O(0,0,0)$ muvozanat (yoki maxsus) nuqta atrofida joylashini o‘rganamiz (1) Sistema yechimini $x_k = \alpha e^{2t}$ ($k = \overline{1,3}$) ko‘rinishida izlaymiz λ ni topish uchun xarakteristik tenglama tuzamiz

$$\Delta(\lambda) = \begin{vmatrix} a_{11} - \lambda & a_{12} & a_{13} \\ a_{21} & a_{22} - \lambda & a_{23} \\ a_{31} & a_{32} & a_{33} - \lambda \end{vmatrix} = 0 \quad (2)$$

Yoki $\lambda^3 + a_1\lambda^2 + a_2\lambda + a_3 = 0$ a_1, a_2, a_3 - lar aniq ko‘paytuvchilarga ikkitasi uchinchi orqali quydagi sistemadan topiladi.

$$\begin{cases} (a_{11} - \lambda)\alpha_1 + a_{12}\alpha_2 + a_{13}\alpha_3 = 0 \\ a_{21}\alpha_1 + (a_{22} - \lambda)\alpha_2 + a_{23}\alpha_3 = 0 \\ a_{31}\alpha_1 + a_{32}\alpha_2 + (a_{33} - \lambda)\alpha_3 = 0 \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

Quyidagi hollarda bo‘lishi mumkin ularni ko‘rib chiqamiz alohida-alohida

a) Xarakteristik tenglamani ildizlari λ_i ($i = \overline{1,3}$) haqiqiy va har xil, u holda uning yechimi $x_k = c_1\beta_k e^{\lambda_1 t} + c_2\gamma_k e^{\lambda_2 t} + c_3\delta_k e^{\lambda_3 t}$ $k = \overline{1,3}$ (4) ko‘rinishda yoziladi.

$\beta_k, \gamma_k, \delta_k$ lar (3) sistemaga mos ravishda $\lambda = \lambda_1, \lambda = \lambda_2, \lambda = \lambda_3$ larni quydagilar orqali topiladi c_1, c_2, c_3 lar erkli o‘zgaras. O‘z navbatida bu yerda quydagi holler bo‘lishi mumkin.

1) barcha i lar uchun $\lambda_i < 0$. U vaqtda muvozanat nuqta $x_1 = 0, x_2 = 0, x_3 = 0$ asimtotik to‘rg‘un, chunki (3) formuladagi ko‘paytuvchi $e^{\lambda_i t}$ lar $t = t_0$ moment koordinatalari boshini δ atrofida bo‘lgan barcha nuqtalar t ning istalga kata qiymatlari uchun koordinatalar boshining

istalgan kichik δ atrofida tushib qoladi va $t \rightarrow \infty$ da koordinatalar boshiga intiladi. 1-chizmada muvozanat nuqta atrofidagi traektoriyalar joylashishi ko‘rsatilgan. Muvozanat turg‘un, tugun turg‘un deyiladi. Strelkalar t o‘shishi bilan traektoriyalar bo‘yicha harakat yo‘nalishini bildiradi. Bu hol (1) Sistema quydagi koefsentli tengsizliklar bajarilishi o‘rinli bo‘ladi.

1- chizma

$$a_1 > 0, \quad \Delta_2 = \begin{vmatrix} a_1 & 1 \\ a_3 & a_2 \end{vmatrix} > 0, \quad a_3 > 0, D < 0.$$

Bu yerda $D = q^2 + p^2$ xarakteristik tenglamaning diskriminanti

$$2q = \frac{2a_1^3}{27} - \frac{a_1 a_2}{3} + a_3, \quad 3p = \frac{3a_2 - a_1^2}{3}$$

2) $\lambda_1 > 0, \lambda_2 > 0, \lambda_3 > 0$ bo‘lsin. Bu holda t ni t ga olmashtersak, yuqorida ko‘rilgan strelkalarini teskari quyish kerak) muvozanat nuqta turg‘unmas tugun deyiladi bu hol koefsentli $a_1 < 0, \Delta_2 < 0, a_2 > 0, D < 0$ tengsizliklar bajarilganda o‘rinli bo‘ladi.

2- chizma

3) Agar $\lambda_1 > 0, \lambda_2 < 0, \lambda_3 < 0$ bo‘lsa, muvozanat nuqta turg‘unmas chunki

$$x_k = c_1 \beta_k e^{\lambda_k t}$$

Traektoriyalar bo‘yicha harakat qiluvchi nuqtalar (c_1 ni qanchalik kichik olmaylik) t o‘shishi bilan koordinatalar boshidagi ε atrofida chiqadi $t \rightarrow \infty$ koordinatalar boshiga intiluvchi harakatlar $x_k = c_2 \gamma_k e^{\lambda_2 t} + c_3 \delta_k e^{\lambda_3 t}$ ko‘rinishda bo‘lib, butun bir tekislikni tashkil qiladi (2-chizma).

(1) sistema $D < 0$ gurbis sharti bajarilgan holda uchraydi

b) Xarakteristik tenglamani ildizlari bajarilmagan holda uchraydi ikkitasi qo‘shma kompleks, ya‘ni $\lambda = \lambda_{1,2,3} = p \pm qi, q \neq 0$ bu holda Sistema uchun umumiy yechim

$$x_k = c_1 \beta_k e^{\lambda_1 t} + e^{pt} (c_2 \cos qt + c_3 \sin qt) \quad k = \overline{1,3} \quad (5)$$

ko‘rinishda bo‘ladi $c_2^i > c_3^i$ lar ($i = 2,3$) c_2^i, c_3^i larning birorta chiziqli konbinatsiyasidan iborat bo‘ladi. Shu sababli bu yerda quydagi holler uchraydi:

1) $\lambda_1 < 0, \lambda_{2,3} = p \pm qi, p < 0, q \neq 0$ ko‘paytuvchi $e^{pt}, p < 0$ t ning o‘shishi bilan nolga intiladi, ikkinchi davriy ko‘paytuvchi (5) formulada har doim chekli bo‘ladi. $t = t_0$

momentda koordinatalar momentda koordinatalar boshining δ atrofida bo‘lgan nuqta traektoriya buylab harakat qilib t ning o‘shishi bilan koordinatalar boshiga yaqinlashib boradi va $t \rightarrow \infty$ da nolga intiladi. Nol yechim- asimtotik turg‘un muvozanat nuqtaga ega turg‘un focus deyiladi (3-chizma).

Bu holda $D > 0$, $a_1 > 0$, $\Delta_2 > 0$, $a_3 > 0$ bo‘ladi.

3-chizma

2) $\lambda_1 > 0, \lambda_{2,3} = p \pm qi$, $p > 0$ $q \neq 0$ bo‘lsin bu yerda t ni t ga almashtersak qolgan hollarga kelamiz. Traektoriyalar joylashishi 3-chizmadagi kabi bo‘ladi, lekin stelkalarteskari quyiladi. Muvozanat nuqta turg‘unmas focus deyiladi.

Bu holda $D > 0$, $a_1 < 0$, $\Delta_2 < 0$, $a_3 > 0$ bo‘ladi

3) Agar $\lambda = \lambda_1, \lambda_{2,3} = p \pm qi$, $p < 0$, $\lambda, q \neq 0$ bo‘lsa (5) formuladagi qushuluvchilardan bittasi o‘sovchi, hisoblanadi $t = t_0$ momenta δ atrofida bo‘lgan t o‘shishi bilan traektoriya bo‘ylab koordinata boshidan uzoqlasha boshlaydi, demak nol yechim turg‘unmas. Muvozanat nuqtaga egar-fokus deyiladi. $D > 0$ bo‘lib, Turvis sharti bajarilmasa muvozanat nuqta egar-fokus bo‘ladi.

4) $\lambda_1, \lambda_{2,3} = \pm qi$, $p = 0$ bo‘lsa λ_1 ning ishorasiga qarab nol yechim turg‘un yoki turg‘unmas bo‘lishi mumkin.

Muvozanat nuqta focus markaz (4-chizma) egar-fokus bo‘lishi mumkin.

4-chizma

b) Xarakteristik ildizlari karrali $\lambda_1 = \lambda_2, \lambda_3$, $\lambda_1 \neq \lambda_3$ ya’ni xarakteristik tenglamani diskriminanti $D = 0$. Bu holda (1) sistemaning umumiy yechimi

$$x_k(t) = (c_1\beta_k + c_2\gamma_k t)e^{\lambda_1 t} + c_3\delta_k e^{\lambda_3 t}, \quad k = \overline{1,3} \quad (6)$$

Kurinishda bo‘lib kupaytuvchi $e^{\lambda_1 k}$, $t \rightarrow \infty$ da nolga intiladi. Shu bilan birga koordinatalar boshining δ - atrofidagi istalgan nuqta t o‘shishi bilan ε - atrofiga tushadi va nolga intiladi. Nol yechim asimtotik turgun bo‘ladi. Muvozanat nuqta turg‘un deyiladi bu holda muvozanat a), 1) bilan turg‘un focus b), 1) orasidagi chigaraviy dolda mos keladi, chunki a_{ij} parametrlari ozroq

o'zgartirilganda muvozanat turg'un tugun, a), 1) holda yoki turg'un fokudga o'tishi mumkin, ya'ni a_{ij} parametriga o'zgarish berilganda xarakteristik tenglamaning karrali ildizlari oddiy haqiqiy yoki qushma kompleks ildizlari ajralishi mumkin.

2) Agar $\lambda_1 = \lambda_2 > 0$, $\lambda_3 > 0$ bo'lsa t ni t ga almashtirilsin 1) holdagi natijaga kelamiz. Faqat traektoriyalar buyicha harakat teskari yo'nalishda bo'ladi. Muvozanat nuqta turg'unmas tugun deyiladi.

3) $\lambda_1 = \lambda_2 > 0$, $\lambda_1 \cdot \lambda_3 < 0$ bo'lsin. Nol yechim tugunmas bo'ladi, chunki (6) formulada $t \rightarrow \infty$ da $\|x(t)\| \rightarrow \infty$. Muvozanat nuqta egar deyiladi, lekin bu egar

a), 3) holdagi egardan farqi shundaki a_{ij} parametrlarni o'zgarterganda a), 3) holdagi egar yoki egar fokus b), 3) dagi tugunga o'tish mumkin, chunki a_{ij} parametrlarning o'zgarishi natijasida ajratilishi mumkin.

a) $\lambda_1 = \lambda_2 = \lambda_3$ bo'lsin. Xarakteristik tenglamaning diskriminantida $D = 0$, (1) Sistema uchun $x_k(t) = (c_1\beta_k + c_2\gamma_k t + c_3\delta_k t^2)e^{\lambda_1 t}$, $k = \overline{1,3}$ (7)

ko'rinishda yoziladi. Quyidagi hollar bo'lishi mumkin .

1) $\lambda_1 < 0$ bo'lsin $e^{\lambda_1 t}$ ko'paytuvchi $t \rightarrow \infty$ da tezroq nolga va shu sababli

$(c_1\beta_k + c_2\gamma_k t + c_3\delta_k t^2)e^{\lambda_1 t}$ ifoda $t \rightarrow \infty$ da nolga intiladi. Nol yechim asimtotik turg'un. Muvozanat nuqta turg'un tugun boladi.

2) $\lambda_2 > 0$ bo'lsin t ni t ga almashtersak, 1) holdagi natijaga kelamiz. Traektoriyalar buyicha harakat teskari yunalishda bo'ladi. Muvozanat nuqta turg'unmas tugun bo'ladi. Xarakteristik sonlar noldan farqli bo'lgan barcha hollarni qarab chiqdik, chunki shartga ko'ra $\det A \neq 0$. Demak yo'qoridagilarga asoslanib tekislikda muvozanat nuqtani quydagicha sinflash mumkin ekan.

a) λ_1 va λ_3 haqiqiy va $\lambda_1 \neq \lambda_3$. Bu holda muvozanat nuqta;

1) $\lambda_1 < 0$, $\lambda_3 < 0$ turg'un tugun;

2) $\lambda_2 > 0$, $\lambda_3 > 0$ turg'unmas tugun;

3) $\lambda_2 < 0$, $\lambda_3 > 0$ turg'unmas egar;

b) $\lambda_{2,3} = q \pm qi$. Bu holda;

1) $p < 0$ turg'un fokus;

2) $p > 0$ turg'unmas focus;

3) $p \neq 0$ markaz tugun;

d) $\lambda_1 = \lambda_3$. Bu holda;

1) $\lambda_2 = \lambda_3 < 0$ turg'un tug'ma tugun;

2) $\lambda_2 = \lambda_3 > 0$ turg'unmas tug'ma tugun;

Agar $\det A = 0$ bo'lgan holda (1) tenglamalar sistemasining muvozanat nuqtalarini kelgusi ishlarimizda sinflaymiz.

Xulosa

Xulosa qilib aytganda bir jinsli uch o'lchovli differensial tenglamalar sistemasini yechimlarinin muvozanat nuqta $O(0,0,0)$ atrofida sinflash uchun tenglamalar sistemasini xarakteristik tenglamasini yechimlari λ_1 , λ_2 , λ_3 larning qiymatlariga qarab

$\det A \neq 0$ da bturg'un tugun, egar focus va turg'unmas tugun , egar focus, markaz ekanligini teksheriladi.

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